

RESIN FLOW DURING AUTOCLAVE PROCESSING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Anoush Poursartip, Golnar Riahi, and Gregory Smith

Composites Group

Department of Metals and Materials Engineering

The University of British Columbia

309-6350 Stores Road

Vancouver, B.C., Canada, V6T 1W5

ABSTRACT

An experimental method to determine the amount of resin flow within a composite laminate during cure is presented. The method is analogous to the use of radioactive tracers in other applications. Heavier elements such as chlorine and bromine, which may be naturally present in small amounts in resins are used to follow resin flow and mixing. The presence and quantity of these tags is determined using wavelength dispersive X-ray analysis. Results for flat net-bleed and zero-bleed laminates are presented. There is considerable flow and mixing in the net-bleed laminate. There is also some very localized flow and mixing in the zero-bleed laminate. The results are discussed in relation to current models for resin flow.

KEYWORDS: Curing; Modeling; Processing; Resin Flow; Resin Tagging.

INTRODUCTION

The scientific processing of thermoset matrix polymers has become an increasingly important area of research in recent years, as the benefits of both optimizing and controlling the processes have become apparent. In this regard, many models have been developed [1-3]. Typically, a complete model consists of a number of sub-models, such as a thermochemical sub-model, a resin flow sub-model, a void sub-model, a residual stress sub-model, and so forth. The interaction between the sub-models is complex and critical, and it is useful to validate each sub-model separately.

This paper presents results from an experimental method that can be used to confirm and guide the development of resin flow sub-models, as well as being used directly in cases where the system is too complicated to be modelled accurately.

In material systems and fabrication routes where the preform is dry, the resin flow wavefront can be determined reasonably easily by using transparent moulds or similar methods. However, to the authors' best knowledge, there are no methods available that allow the determination of the degree of resin flow in systems where the resin and fibre are already mixed. Currently, in the case of laminates, the amount of resin flow is generally estimated on the basis of mass loss from the composite [1], mass increase of the bleeder layers [1], the level of compaction of the laminate stack [4], sectioning and measuring ply thicknesses [5], and so forth.

A method is presented in this paper that allows the determination of the local resin volume fraction in any ply, as well as the amount of resin in that ply that came from a specified (and tagged) ply or section of a ply. The method is applied here to the autoclave curing of laminates, but obviously can be used in any thermoset resin fabrication route.

EXPERIMENTS

The concept of tagging materials with radioactive tracers is a well known method that has been used successfully in the study of the solidification behaviour of metals. Similarly, elemental analysis is used routinely during scanning electron microscopy to identify and quantify the presence of different elements.

In the case of polymers, two factors have barred the use of elemental analysis. Firstly, most probes are unable to register quantitatively the presence of the major constituents, namely carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen, and oxygen, because of their low atomic weight. Secondly, as most polymers are similar in their constituents (but differ in the nature of the bonding), elemental analysis is not particularly helpful.

However, if we combine the concept of resin tagging and elemental analysis, we have a method that is of use in determining resin flow. In many resin systems, small amounts of other elements are sometimes added. A typical and useful example is the addition of bromine to promote fire-retardancy. Bromine is easily detected with elemental analysis. So long as the bromine distribution in the original tagged resin is uniform, and the bromine is distributed during processing by flow of the tagged resin, rather than by diffusion of the bromine alone, then a map of the bromine distribution through the laminate is a measure of the flow of the tagged resin.

Thus if one layer or part of a layer in a multi-layered laminate is tagged, and the final bromine distribution throughout the laminate is mapped, a measure of the flow of resin from the tagged layer into all other layers is available. By comparison with the relevant resin and element standards, a quantitative measure of the flow can be obtained. At this stage we have a measure of the amount of tagged resin in any layer, but ideally we require also the total amount of resin in each layer.

We can overcome this obstacle by noting that most epoxy resins are in essence already tagged with another element, chlorine, during their synthesis. Epichlorohydrin is used in the synthesis of epoxy resins, and remains present in small amounts in the final product. As our results have shown [6], the amounts are small, but nevertheless sufficient to allow an adequate determination of the total resin volume fraction.

Full details of the method and a statistical analysis of the accuracy of the method are provided in reference [6]. We note here that the quantitative analysis is performed using wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (WDX) in a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Care must be taken to ensure a high enough count rate to achieve an acceptable level of accuracy. Given that the beam accelerating voltage is 20 kV, the electron beam penetrates the surface of the specimen to a depth of about 5 μm . This is sufficient to ensure that a representative volume is being measured, so that there is no need to have the fibres normal to the surface. The depth of penetration is determined by the beam accelerating voltage, but the width and length of the monitored area can be set independently by rastering the beam accordingly. We have chosen our representative area to be roughly 90 by 70 μm . This choice is determined by the need to be small enough to resolve volume fractions in each layer, but large enough to get a representative volume. The volume of measurement is therefore approximately 90 by 70 by 5 μm . If we consider the two extremes of fibre orientation, it is clear that when the fibres are normal to the exposed surface the excited volume is representative of the layer. When the fibres are parallel to the exposed surface, the excited volume is also representative of the layer because the depth of the zone is equal to or larger than the fibre *radius*. At lower excitation voltages this is not true, and readings at any fibre orientation other than normal to the surface would be misleading.

The raw data collected from a WDX analysis is in the form of the total number of counts registered in a specified time at a certain wavelength. Apart from statistical randomness, this count is directly proportional to the number of atoms of the element of interest present. It is therefore a measure of the mass of that element in the measured volume. Given that the ratio of the mass of tracer element to the mass of resin is unchanged, then the WDX reading is a measure of the mass of the resin present in the measured volume. To convert this reading into a resin volume fraction, one must assume that the resin density is constant, or alternatively, allow for any density changes. Density changes in fully cured epoxy resins are typically very small. Even where there is incomplete cure, the resin density is constant beyond a degree of cure of about 0.4. It is worthy of emphasis that the fibre density plays no role in determining the resin volume fraction when using the WDX approach.

Example 1

In this example, a flat cross-plyed sixteen layer laminate was fabricated, with only the fifteenth layer containing brominated ICI Fiberite 7714 resin. The other layers contained ICI Fiberite 7409 non-brominated resin. The edges of the stack were dammed so that only vertical flow

could occur into the bleeder plies. The laminate was fully cured and compacted, and then sectioned and analyzed using WDX. Both chlorine and bromine counts were taken for each layer. Since the laminate is a cross-ply, each layer is identified easily, and analyzed separately. Two traverses were made through the thickness of the laminate, approximately 20 mm apart. For each traverse, two 10 second readings were taken, one on each side of the centre-line of the traverse, and averaged. The raw counts were converted to volume fractions. Full details are provided in Reference [6].

Figure 1. Fibre volume (%) as determined by WDX analysis, as a function of layer number for two traverses through the thickness. Layer 15 is the tagged layer.

The total volume fraction of fibres in each layer is shown in Figure 1. The error bar which is shown is the calculated worst possible error, and is from the uncertainty in the chlorine counts (which are considerably lower than the bromine counts). Apart from the differences at the two surfaces of the laminate (layers 1,2,and 16) the two traverses, 20 mm apart, show remarkably similar total volume fractions of about 76 %. Allowing for different layer thicknesses (which are also measured in the SEM), the laminate volume fraction is estimated at 81 %, which compares very well with the independent value of 80 % calculated from a knowledge of the initial fibre and resin masses and the final laminate mass and dimensions.

Figure 2. Fraction of brominated resin 1 (Fiberite 7714) in total resin content, as determined by WDX analysis, as a function of layer number for two traverses through the thickness. Layer 15 is the tagged layer.

Of greater interest is the fraction of brominated resin in the total resin content in each layer, as shown in Figure 2. The two traverses show that the brominated resin, originally only in layer 15, has flowed quite far. Traverse #1 shows continuous resin flow as far as layer 8, whereas traverse #2 shows a more rapid decrease in brominated resin content away from layer 15, but instead a small pocket of brominated resin can be seen in layers 8 and 9. The absolute values indicate that layer 15 is still 90% brominated resin at the end of the compaction, and that significant amounts of brominated resin are present in many layers.

Example 2

Whereas in the previous example the excess resin was allowed to flow out of the laminate, another experiment was performed where 'zero-bleed' conditions were applied. In this condition there are no bleeder layers and all the resin remains in the laminate. In our case, the average prepreg resin content was 46%. However, two new resins, ICI Fiberite 7740 and 7740-X were used. The former is non-brominated, whereas the latter was specially brominated and provided for these experiments by the manufacturer. As a result, the viscosity profiles, densities, and other properties of these two resins are far better matched than in Example 1.

As in the previous example, a sixteen layer cross-ply laminate was laid up and cured according to the manufacturers recommended cure cycle, with the tagged (brominated) resin in the fifteenth layer. The laminate was sectioned, and bromine and chlorine counts taken for each layer at three positions in the middle of the laminate, approximately 10 mm apart.

Through-the-thickness averages of the fibre volume fraction were 48.3, 50.4, and 51.6 % respectively, in reasonable agreement with the measured prepreg value.

According to current thinking, there should be no resin flow in a flat zero-bleed laminate. However, the bromine readings in layers 14 and 16 at the three monitored positions were high, indicating some degree of flow. Furthermore there were large variations between them. Therefore, the area between two positions was mapped carefully with 27 sets of readings taken over a distance of about 10 mm. At each of these positions two readings were taken in each layer, one above the other, so as to increase through-the-thickness resolution. Each layer was scanned for bromine only. No bromine was detected above layer 13. Therefore, a very detailed map of the bromine distribution, and hence the tagged resin distribution, was generated for the lower four layers.

Results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. These figures show the results in different forms, as it is difficult to visualize the results without resorting to colour contour maps. Figure 3 shows the variation of the resin 1 (brominated or tagged resin) volume fraction as a function of horizontal distance from the first position. A separate line is plotted for each horizontal traverse through the cross-section. Each layer has two horizontal traverses, one above the other, to provide better through-the-thickness resolution. The exception is layer 16, which is the layer adjacent to the toolplate. It was not possible to take a set of readings next to the free surface, as the presence of the free surface introduces gross errors. As can be seen, layers 15 and 16 have very high concentrations of brominated resin 1 (which was originally in layer 15). Layer 14 also contains brominated resin 1, but to a much lesser extent. There is no brominated resin 1 in layer 13.

An alternative way to interpret the results is the contour map in Figure 4. The contours are for the brominated resin 1 volume fraction in 0.02 increments, with the solid lines indicating values of 0.1, 0.2, and 0.3 respectively. This contour plot is very effective at showing that there is considerable localized mixing, especially within layers 15 and 16.

Figure 3. Variation of volume fraction of brominated resin 1, originally from layer 15, throughout layers 14 to 16. Results are for a 10 mm long strip in the centre of the laminate.

Figure 4. Contour map of the brominated resin 1 originally from layer 15 now in layers 13 to 16. Each contour represents a change of 0.02 in volume fraction. There is no brominated resin 1 in layer 13.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

We consider first the net-bleed system in Example 1. Current flow models can be split into two groups. The first, as developed by Springer and co-workers (for example [1]) assumes that the fibre bed carries no load, and that there is a compaction wavefront travelling through the laminate, starting from the bleeder interface, and eventually reaching the toolplate. As a result of the assumptions in the model, it predicts that the resin flow will be laminar and sequential. For example, the excess resin in layer n next to the toolplate is pushed into layer $n-1$ last of all, the excess resin in layer $n-2$ having been pushed into layer $n-3$ and so forth. The second set of flow models, as developed by Gutowski and co-workers [2], and by Dave and co-workers [3], develop a pressure profile based on considerations of load sharing between resin and fibre bed and other assumptions. As a result it is possible to get a significantly non-linear through-the-thickness pressure profile.

The pressure gradient through the thickness, coupled with the local viscosities and permeabilities, is used in conjunction with Darcy's Law to provide a value for the local resin velocity. In the case of the Springer approach, a single velocity is calculated, and is representative of the whole compacted zone. In the Gutowski/Dave approach, there can be a velocity gradient through the thickness. Therefore, the resin mixing seen in the current experimental work is not possible with the Springer flow model, at least not without some modifications. The Gutowski/Dave flow models could allow for mixing, especially in the case where the resin in one layer has a higher velocity than the resin in a layer closer to the bleeder interface.

The results presented in Figure 2 can be compared with the Springer model in a qualitative fashion. The Springer model [1] has been coded using an object oriented language to run under Microsoft Windows on an IBM PC. The code keeps track of all resin movement between layers, and it is possible to plot the resin distribution, including the origin of the resin, as a function of position through the thickness at any time during the cure cycle. It is therefore ideally suited for comparison with the results presented here.

In Example 1, two different resin systems were used, and furthermore not all the necessary material data for running the Springer model were available. Therefore, for the purposes of a qualitative comparison, we use the viscosity, cure, and other parameters as provided in Ref [1]. Material data such as initial and final layer thickness and other easily measured values were taken from the actual experiment. Plotted in Figure 5 are the resin flow profiles for an arbitrary time t , where the instantaneous viscosity is low (about 1 Pa.s, which is the lowest for both the 3501-6 resin in Ref [1] and in the resins used here). Figure 5 is therefore representative of the time when the bulk of the resin flow occurs.

Two predictions are presented in Figure 5. The first prediction is for the case of true laminar flow. This is the type of flow envisaged in Ref [1]. This is in disagreement with the

experimental results, as well as the more complex models of Dave and Gutowski. However, the Springer model has the advantage of simplicity. Therefore, one option is to enable some degree of mixing in the Springer model by arbitrarily allowing perfect mixing of the resin in each layer at each time-step. This mixing within a layer forms the basis for the second prediction in Figure 5. As can be seen, this prediction is now similar to the experimental results presented in Figure 2.

Figure 5. Comparison of predictions of the Springer model for flow and mixing of resin assuming laminar flow or arbitrarily assuming perfect resin mixing in each layer at every time interval.

Figure 2 is replotted in Figure 6, with the addition of two prediction curves from the Springer model, modified to allow perfect mixing of the resins within a layer. The experimental results from the two traverses can be fitted quite well by two predictions based on times 60 seconds apart. Compared to cure cycles of the order of thousands of seconds, this is not unreasonable, particularly since most of the flow occurs while the viscosity is low.

We consider next the zero-bleed system of Example 2. Inspection of Figures 3 and 4 shows that there are about 9 peaks or vortices over a distance of about 10 mm. The bundle diameter of the 6K AS4 fibre tow used to make the prepreg is about 1 mm. Even though optical inspection of the cross-section of the laminate shows no discrete bundles of fibres within the layers, one explanation of the patterns seen in Figures 3 and 4 is preferential flow through the areas of high permeability between the fibre bundles. Another possibility is the creation of unsteady, free convection cells (Benard cells) [7] due to a combination of small temperature gradients and the density differential between fibre and resin. In comparison, the net-bleed system in Example 1 shows a much more uniform horizontal distribution. This is most likely because the large volumes of flow in a net-bleed system lead to a complete and uniform

mixing profile. In the zero-bleed system, the amount of flow is very small and localized, leading to large local variations.

Figure 6. Comparison of experimental results with the Springer model predictions using arbitrary assumption of perfect mixing of resins (see text).

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